

AQUASERV PID:36691-IbonCancio-phagoTOR

Version 2

Description

This DMP defines the type of data that will be obtained from the Aquaserv transnational access project phagoTor (PID:36691) carried out during a whole reproductive cycle of O. mykiss rainbow trouts in the INRAE farm in the Pyrenees (cold waters). Samples collected monthly will be processed for biochemical, histological and molecular studies in different tissues and organs.

Funder

Grant

Researchers

Ibon Cancio (0000-0003-4841-0079), Oihane Diaz de cerio (0000-0002-5605-8434), Lucie Marandel (0000-0001-9395-6041), Clarissa Atzori (0009-0005-8934-1032), Emilie Cardona (0000-0001-9270-5187)

Organizations

PiE-UPV/EHU

1. Main Info

Title of Plan: [AQUASERV PID:36691-IbonCancio-phagoTOR](#)

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Organizations:

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Contact: [Cancio Ibon \(ibon.cancio@ehu.eus\)](mailto:ibon.cancio@ehu.eus)

Access: [Public](#)

2. Ethics

Introduction:

The experimental procedure, including the food deprivation regime adopted, was previously discussed with the access providers in INRAE-STPEE and after internal discussion (referring veterinarian and animal welfare structure) it was certified that no evaluation of the procedure was required by their ethical board (restriction is a current practise in broodstock trout breeding and all samplings will be done on euthanised fish). Fish will be euthanised following the usual approved procedures in the access provider using MS-222.

3. Dataset descriptions

Introduction:

Metadata regarding rearing conditions, food characteristics, and data on total body weight, liver and ovary weight, visceral mass and GSI and HSI derived from there.

Histological images.

Biochemical data on nutrient accumulation.

Hormonal levels

Electropherograms of total RNA extracted from trout ovaries.

qPCR data.

Descriptions

[AQUASERV](#) | [all categories](#) | [generic template](#)

Considering that ovarian development is synchronous in rainbow trout, and that the INRAE facilities manages an autumnal strain with reproduction occurring in winter (November-December), the experiment will last from January to September, allowing to cover a whole ovarian developmental process until 2ry growth or cortical alveoli oocytes stage in June and full maturation at the end of September. 6 tanks to maintain two groups in triplicates (3 normal fed and 3 restricted diet) are needed and in total 12 (2x3 + 2x3) fish will be sacrificed monthly for the analyses. Food restriction conditions will be achieved feeding animals every Monday, Tuesday, Thursday and Friday. Feed will be the formulated commercial feed used in INRAE-STPEE. Sampling, will be conducted to histologically describe the oogenic cycle as it has not been described yet for this stock maintained at 8°C. Histological ranking will be complemented by molecular analysis of the 5S/18S rRNA

index that has been widely published. The index has not been yet validated in trout. Plasma samples will be collected to measure steroid hormone levels in all sampled individuals (oestradiol, 11-ketotestosterone, progesterone, cortisol). Blood will be extracted from the caudal vein, centrifuged to recover plasma and stored at -20°C for hormone analyses through UV-HPLC.

Ovaries are expected to initiate secondary growth and reaching cortical alveoli stage in June, when atresia is hypothesised to be manifested at its most in the food deprived group (monthly samplings will characterise the exact moment for this sampling). During these 2 extensive samplings, six fish per group (two per tank) will be euthanised using the usual procedure in INRAE-STPEE (MS-222 anaesthetic overdose). For molecular analyses brain, liver, and ovary will be dissected, embedded in RNAlater®, frozen in liquid N2 and stored at -80°C until further use. The same will be done with another portion of the ovary without RNA later, for western blot analyses of target proteins in the mTOR pathway and the autophagocytosis process. Other portions of ovaries will be directly frozen in liquid N2 for cryostat sectioning and histochemical identification of lysosomal marker enzymes (β -GUS, AcP and HEX). Additional ovary portions will be fixed in formalin and paraffin embedded for histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis.

Food and whole carcass of individuals sampled on the 1st and the last month will be analysed for total nutrient content (dry matter, ash, total protein, total lipids, energy, carbohydrates)

Nutrient contents will be assessed in plasma and ovaries. Glucose/glycogen, total lipids and fatty acids, and freed amino acids profiles will be analysed banking on the expertise in the field of INRAE-STPEE. The relative transcription levels of target genes will be determined in ovaries (also vitellogenin in liver and gonadotropins in pituitary) by qPCR as described in Rojo-Bartolomé et al (2016). Histochemically stained slides will allow visualising the lysosomal compartment and calculating stereological parameters via Image-J. This will help to anchor phenotypically the PCR analysis of autophagocytosis. We shall also measure ribogenesis marker genes (5S/18S rRNA index through capillary electrophoresis of RNA and gt3ab by qPCR, Rojo-Bartolomé et al 2016; Bir et al 2023) to monitor oocyte growth vs death.

Template: [AQUASERV](#) | [all categories](#) | [generic template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

No

1.1.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Images from histological sections of trout ovaries (.jpeg)

Excell files with metadata (broodstock management, feed composition, size of experimental animals, GSI, HSI)

Excell files with biochemical data (nutrients in tissues)

Excell files with hormonal profiles

Agilent Bioanalyzer profiles of total RNA (electropherograms)

Excell files with qPCR results

1.1.3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Obtention of results on the effects of diet restriction in ovarian development in rainbow trout and comparison with other fish species and broodstock management

1.1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

In excell files just some Kbytes

In histological images in the order of Terabytes

In Agilent electropherograms some Kbytes

1.1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Ovaries, liver, brain and blood of 2 year old female rainbow trout (*O. mykiss*) from the stock of INRAE-Stpee and Leés-Athas

1.1.6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Aquaculture, fish biology, fisheries research, endocrine disruption, nutrition, molecular and cell biology

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

This DMP will be published through zenodo

2.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes

Broodstock management, feed composition, size of experimental animals during the experiments and at sampling, gonadosomatic index (GSI), hepatosomatic index (HSI)

2.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

No

Unless help is received data will be findable but accessible using the same tools we have at hand

2.2 Making data accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Zenodo

2.2.1.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Registered in Zenodo

2.2.2 Data

2.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Until publication of results in peer review journals

2.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

No

2.2.3 Metadata

2.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes

2.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

This will be necessary for histological slides scanned through a high resolution slide scanner and for electropherograms obtained after capillary electrophoresis in Agilent Bioanalyzer

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Other

Published in peer reviewed papers

2.4.2 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

3 Data security

3.1 Data security

3.1.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

None

3.1.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

Zenodo

4 Other research outputs

4.1 Making other research outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1 Will other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

No

4.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

No

4.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

At least using the same tools we have at hand

4.2 Making other research outputs accessible

4.2.2 Other research outputs

4.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research outputs should be made available as soon as possible.

Until published in peer-reviewed journals

4.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the other research outputs, both during and after the end of the project?

Free from zenodo

4.2.3 Metadata

4.2.3.1 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the other research outputs?

Yes

4.2.3.2 How long will the other research outputs remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after other research outputs is no longer available?

As above

4.2.3.3 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the other research outputs be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

As above

4.3 Making other research outputs interoperable

4.3.1 What other research outputs and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your other research outputs interoperable to allow other research outputs exchange and re-use within and

across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

As above

4.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

As above

4.4 Increase other research outputs re-use

4.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate other research outputs analysis and facilitate other research outputs re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, research outputs cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Other

Publication in peer reviewed journals

4.4.2 Will your other research outputs be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your other research outputs be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Allocation of resources

5.1.1 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Direct cost

5.1.2 How will these be covered?

We do not have data people

6 Ethics

6.1 Ethics

6.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No

6.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No

7 Other issues

7.1 Other issues

7.1.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No

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